

A STUDY ON ANALYZING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TRADITIONAL AND DIGITAL PROMOTIONAL ACTIVITIES WITH REFERENCE TO TATA MOTORS

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, with the appearance of social media, traditional print and broadcast media as main promotional tools have faced major challenges, as many newspapers and television channels have suffered audience reduction. Overwhelmingly, the majority of marketers, both business and political, have started to use some form of social media for promotional purposes. The overall purpose of this research is to characterize the similarities and differences of the use of social media as promotional tool by political parties and companies. This research is exploratory in nature and the data collected is qualitative. In order to conduct this research, we have interviewed two political parties and two companies. Taking into account the new communication paradigm from Man gold and Faulds as a base, we asked questions about how they use each element of the promotional mix in social media. The findings showed that the use of social media for promotional purposes was rather similar between the companies and political parties. Analyzed data showed that political parties, in their social media activities, were focused on public relations and personal selling in a form of online interactions with voters, while the companies only focused on public relations. This research demonstrates that both political parties and companies still have not fully integrated social media for promotional purposes and that they still rely on traditional media for promotion.

Measure the impact of marketing activities on decisions to visit the platform and on decisions to create and buy content. The model explains individual-level choices as a function of

consumer characteristics and marketing activities, allowing for interdependence of decisions within and across users. Our results compare four types of marketing activities: price promotions, firm online activities, content creator referrals, and public relations efforts. We show that price promotions have strong effects on purchases, while content creator referrals and public relations have significant effects on all user decisions.

An interesting feature of the data is that the price distribution in the absence of promotional activities first order stochastically dominates that under display or feature advertising. The theoretical model we introduce can yield an equilibrium that is consistent with the above observations

1. INTRODUCTION

Promotion is true that products are manufactured to satisfy the needs of the consumers.. But alone is not enough. Today the responsibility of the manufacturers does not cease with physical production whatever may be the nature of the product. The present day marketers are consumer oriented where it is the duty of the manufacturers to know from where, when, how and what price the products would be available. Successful marketing consists in offering the right product of the right price of the right place (and time) with right promotion.

In course of time, various activities came into vogue designed particularly to help easy sale of goods. These activities commonly known as promotional Mix. The marketing

communication Mix also called as the “Promotion Mix” consists of four major tools.

1. Advertising.
2. **Sales Promotion**
3. Publicity
4. Personal Selling

Generally marketing communication is undertaken to pass on the message of a product or sale to the ultimate consumers. Thus, there are three elements in this process.

The purpose of advertising is motivating but to sell something a product, a service or Reliance. The real objective of advertising is effective communication between producers and consumers. In other words the ultimate purpose all advertising is “Increased awareness” list of the following specific objectives of advertising.

The process of selling is ensured by personal selling supposed by advertising and sales promotion. Of these three methods personal selling occupies the predominant role mainly because of the personal element involves. It may be described as a personal source rendered to the community in connection with marketing of goods.

It is a marketing process with which consumers are personally persuaded to by goods and services offered by a manufacturer. The most powerful element in the promotional mix is salesman ship, is not something very new. Even centuries ago salesman ship was practiced in Greece and Rome. According to Peter Drucker Cyrus Mecornie was the first man to use modern technique of selling.

Promotion activities

Sales promotion is one of the seven aspects of the promotional mix. (The other six parts of the promotional mix are advertising, personal selling, direct marketing, publicity/public relations, corporate image and exhibitions.) Media and non-media marketing communication are employed for a pre-determined, limited time to increase consumer demand, stimulate market demand or improve product availability. Examples include contests, coupons, freebies,

loss leaders, point of purchase displays, premiums, prizes, product samples, and rebates

Sales promotions can be directed at either the customer, sales staff, or distribution channel members (such as retailers). Sales promotions targeted at the consumer are called **consumer sales promotions**. Sales promotions targeted at retailers and wholesale are called **trade sales promotions**. Some sale promotions, particularly ones with unusual methods, are considered gimmicks by many.

Sales promotion includes several communications activities that attempt to provide added value or incentives to consumers, wholesalers, retailers, or other organizational customers to stimulate immediate sales. These efforts can attempt to stimulate product interest, trial, or purchase. Examples of devices used in sales promotion include coupons, samples, premiums, point-of-purchase (POP) displays, contests, rebates, and sweepstakes.

Need and Importance of the Study:

The increasing competition in business is the reason to pay much more attention to satisfying customers. It may help the market to notice role of customer satisfaction in the overall context of product of service development and management.

Customers do not buy services, they buy satisfaction. Hence marketers must be clear about the satisfaction the customer is seeking and check out whether the customers are getting the actual satisfaction. This study helps the marketers to take necessary steps to gain the competitive advantage over the competitors.

The study helps to predict further behavior intentions of the customers such as intention to re-purchase, intention to increase the usage, intention to recommend the product and Service to others. Today the customers have wide variety of motorcycles to chose.

If the satisfaction level of the customer goes down he may switch over to other brand. Ultimately the company loses its actual

customers. This study helps the marketer to take necessary steps to overcome this problem and retain in the increase of customer loyalty.

2. Objectives of the Study:

- To study the promotional activities offered by **TATA Motors limited.**
- To identify the impact of sales in the market by using promotional strategies of **TATA Motors limited.**
- To study the influence of schemes offered by firm on sales.
- To study the customer's awareness towards the after sale services offered to him or her.
- To find out the factors that influences to the buy **TATA Motors.**
- To identify and study the problems faced by the consumers of **TATA Motor Services.**
- To study the satisfaction level of exist **TATA consumer of TATA Motor Services.**
- To assess the role of brand image in the purchase **TATA Motors.**

Scope of Study:

The scope is confirmed only to examine the "Customer relationship management with reference to **Tata Motors services**" and to find possible remedies to counteract their competition.

The study aims to measure satisfaction level of the dealers regarding **Tata Motors** industries. The area within which the study was conducted regarding the information the primary data is collected in the form of questionnaire collected from the dealers in Ranga reddy district.

The research measures the experiences of customers. Defines and analyses the experiences based on key deliverables. Gains insights into Customer expectations.

3. Methodology of the study:

Data collected method:

The data is collected through close ended questionnaire.

a) Source of data:

1) Primary Data:

The primary data is collected through questionnaires from the customers.

2) Secondary Data:

The secondary data is collected from the books, journals and internet.

b) Sample size:

1. The sample size of the survey (N) is 100.
2. Samples are collected customers of showroom.
3. The age limit of the customers is in between 20-55.
4. The customers will be randomly selected.

c) **Tools & Techniques:** For analyzing the data statistical tables, percentages, and bar-diagrams will be used.

d) **Further scope of study;** The topic of promotional activities is vast there is further scope of study for eg; Advertising, sales promotion etc.

e) **Kind of research:** The research study will be carried out in qualitative and quantitative research approaches.

The research has to be done in very efficient way; the frame work for collecting data is called research design.

The statistical involves the study of a few factors in large number of cased. The contents of research design are

- i) Data collected method.
- ii) Research instrument.

f) **Survey approach:** The survey will be conducted through close ended questionnaire. This questionnaire will contain the multiple choice

questions; each question will be given options. The collection of data in survey follows two types they are

- i) Primary data (first hand data).
- ii) Secondary data (used data).

LIMITATIONS

- Time is an important constraint. The whole study was conducted in a period of 45 days.
- The Study is Restricted to a limited region i.e., the twin cities of Hyderabad and Secunderabad. So, the inferences made by this study are not applicable to the entire market.
- The data collection from the respondents is qualitative in nature i.e., views, opinions, etc., so it is not a convenient data for the study for a longer duration.
- The Respondents were very apprehensive while taking the telephone number and address.
- I consulted only public, customers of TATA only. I collected only 100 samples.

4. ACTIVITIES UNDER THE 4P ARE OF THE MARKETING MIX:

1) Product:

Managing the product includes planning and developing the right products and services to be marketed by the company policy strategy guidelines are needed for changing the existing products and adding new ones.

A product activity includes policies and procedures relating to:

- a. Product variety, quality, features, design, brand name, packaging, size, services, warranties and returns.
- b. Markets to sell-whom, where and in what quantity.
- c. New product policy, R&D programs.

2) Pricing activities:

Include policies and procedures relating to

1. List prices.
2. Discounts.
3. Allowances.
4. Payment period.
5. Credit terms.

Generally markets consider the following factors while seeking price: target customers, cost, competition, social responsibility.

3) Promotional activities:

Includes policies and procedures relating to.

- Advertising: media mix, budget, allocation and programmers.
- Personal setting: objectives, quality of sales force, cost level, level of motivation.
- Promotion: special setting plans/ devices directed at or through the trade forms of these devices are consumer promotions and trade opinions.
- Publicity and public relations.

4) Place/distribution activities: Basically place of distribution activities are to transfer ownership to consumer and to place products, services, idea at the right time and place. Distribution is made up of two components

- 1) Physical distribution and
- 2) Channels of distribution
 - i) Physical distribution: Activities involved in moving products or services from producer to consumer are.
 - Transportation, warehousing and storage, order processing and inventory control.
 - ii) Channels of distribution;: These are the routes taken by good from producer-consumer it includes.
 - Channel design
 - Location of outlets
 - Channel remuneration

